

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:04:21 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	12.82	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.1956	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:04:21 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	5.284	μm	
Min:	-3.245	μm	
Max:	2.038	μm	
Size:	270157	digits	
Spacing:	0.01956	nm	
NM-points ratio:	5.605 % (504460 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:04:21 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	5.284	μm	
Size:	270157	digits	
Spacing:	0.01956	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λ_s): [Workflow] S-filtered (λ_s 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.5822	μm	
Ssk	-1.147		
Sku	7.292		
Sp	2.032	μm	
Sv	3.252	μm	
Sz	5.284	μm	
Sa	0.4079	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	1.987	%	
Smc	0.6208	μm	
Sxp	1.508	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	16.16	μm	
Str	0.7493		
Std	86.51	$^\circ$	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2396		
Sdr	2.617	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02715	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	0.6480	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.02715	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	0.3928	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	0.5465	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.1015	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	3.768	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.6611	µm
Mean density of furrows	3972	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	135.0	°
Second direction	90.02	°
Third direction	0.01421	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	86.42	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

Information

Method Length-scale (rows)

Parameters Value Unit Comment

epLsar ***** Length-scale anisotropy (Sfrac) (1.8 nm, 5°)

NewEplsar ***** Length-scale anisotropy (1.8 nm, 5°)

Information

Method Area-scale (four corners)

Parameters Value Unit Comment

Asfc 5.235 Fractal complexity

Smfc 3972359 nm² Scale of max complexity

HAsfc9 0.3601 Heterogeneity of Asfc (3x3)

HAsfc81 0.8335 Heterogeneity of Asfc (9x9)